

Reflections from ethics towards the ethics of life

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This article presents reflections that revolve around ethics about the names that have been given to it for its study in an environmental context. A state of the relationship between human beings and nature is presented, together with the effect of their actions and behaviors, and it is established that their conduct must be considered within the framework of responsibility aimed at caring for life. The authors nourish the reflection from the perspectives of the different types of ethics with their respective founding authors, in addition to the review of sympathetic and detractor positions; likewise, pillars are postulated for the constitution of ethics of life supported by substantial aspects, such as an invitation to examine an ethic whose purpose stipulates the survival of life.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The various forms of perception that human societies have of nature vary from those that have conducts or behaviors that favor the stability or balance of each of the components of the ecosystems and their interactions [1], to behaviors that do not recognize the importance of nature or consider it as a relational body that allows the existence of all living beings on the planet, including the human being within a biotic community in any territory [2].

There are conceptual and theoretical dynamics where the human being defines and structures mechanisms of conduct, rules, and behaviors, to connote that there must be a substantial change in the way of life of human population groups whose actions are deteriorating the living system called Earth; In this sense, ethical approaches arise promoted by important managers such as Fritz Jahr in 1927, followed by Aldo Leopold in 1949 and Van Rensselaer Potter in 1988 [3], wherewith their positions they generate a process of recognition towards the ethics of human action in its survival and establish postulates that include the context of the totality, that is, of everything living and non-living [4], of the effect of human actions on other living organisms and non-living elements [5], and the importance of establishing behaviors with responsibilities towards the environment, to preserve and conserve life [6].

It is worth noting that the interaction between humans and nature generates a variety of links [7], some stronger than others, which may depend on the proximity to the natural resources used for their progress within a geolocated space. Where the link is close, human behaviors of deep respect for Mother Earth can be perceived [8], on the contrary, weak and very distant links, can translate into an uprooting from nature and lead to behavior where the excessive use and consumption of natural resources is normalized and becomes a pattern of exploitation of nature [9], and consequently, a relational rupture of the human being with the care of nature [10].

From the perspective of uprooting and the lack of recognition of the human being towards nature, seen only as a vehicle for its use for exclusive purposes, and not as a subject with which a relational situation is built, in which harmony must be sought and human activities must be carried out responsibly and the role of ethical responsibility is assumed in the face of the consequences of their actions [11]. Thus, in this way, a path can be started that fosters an integrated human being, with his being and with his natural environment [12], with ethical acting for and with nature, where the preservation and conservation of natural resources, ecosystems, and their components, in itself, of all life on the planet, is prioritized [13].

Consequently, as described above, this study reflects on the conceptual evolution and postulates given by different ethics, such as Bioethics, Earth Ethics, Global Bioethics, Environmental Ethics, Ecological Bioethics, Planetary Ethics, and Ecoethics. These reflections from founding authors and followers allow us to propose and establish ethical pillars for life, such as Ecocentrism, Biocentrism, Expansionism, Transforming Agent, and Ecosophy. Finally, the authors express the importance of rescuing constituent aspects from the dialogue of ethics that lead to an ethics of life for survival.

2. METHOD

In the present research, a documentary study was carried out based on the recorded findings using the ethical search chain of life or ethics of life in the following databases: Redalyc- Clacso, Dialnet, Jstor, Doaj, Latindex, ProQuest, Scielo, ScienceDirect and Web of Science. Subsequently, it was necessary to establish inclusion criteria for the more detailed and in-depth selection of the supporting documents for this document, which were: 1) that the search string was found exactly and inserted in the title or the author's keywords or in the summary, 2) the documentary typology corresponding to review articles and research articles were taken into account, 3) the period of publication of the documents was established between 2023 and 2014, and 4) five disciplinary areas were defined about the categories of this study, according to the databases consulted and in affinity with the names of the different areas given by them, philosophy, anthropology, geography, social sciences, and environmental sciences were included; finally, 5) freely accessible documents were chosen. Consequently, based on the results reported from the analysis of 39 main documents as primary sources, the authors propose reflective chapters in the results and analysis

section from the study of the articles that allow proposing classifications from different perspectives to ethics and their contributions, based on ecology, the environment and the relationship with the survival of the life of organisms and their surroundings, the above allows to confront arguments in two ways.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Approaches to Ethics

- Bioethics, Fritz Jahr in 1927, is considered one of the pioneers in proposing an ethics from the term Bioethics, and by its environmental spirit generated by the environmental deterioration that occurred in its time, proposes an ethics that *considers the human being as an integral part of a broad biotic community that goes beyond the limits of the human being; consequently, Jahr himself calls the bioethical action, is translated in the field of the relational, in his terms in the world of relationships that human beings establish between ourselves and with the environment as a whole; The above, calls for a bioethics with the imperative moral purpose of considering ourselves beings equal to animals and plants, and thus find a balance between the values and purposes of life, all so that existing life forms survive and meet their needs, all without exclusions or preferences* [3].

However, Jahr's position of equality and balance of living beings could be considered as an absurd approach for the time in which it was generated, the beginning of the 20th century, in which human beings should have certain obligations to other living beings. The term bioethics marks a difference from that of ethics since it emphasizes the necessary relationship between ethical values and biological events that are not involved when analyzing the social and environmental problems of individuals and collectivities to achieve the acceptable survival of humanity in the long term [14]. However, bioethics has the main challenge of the integration of all individuals, not only humans, since all are part of the same community, although it is considered imperative to promote a theoretical framework based on the functional relationships of and between communities of individuals, where the ethical dimension is highlighted [15].

- The Ethics of the Earth, Aldo Leopold in 1949, postulated an extension to ethics where he intended to broaden the moral framework of the human subject with the interaction of the entire set made up of all biotic organisms with a purpose, the evolutionary possibility and as an ecological necessity. The ethics of the Earth, therefore, must deal with the relationship of man with animals, with the Earth and the plants that grow on it; so it would be important to address a reconceptualization of the limits of a community, in this should be included the soil, water, animals, and plants explicitly; in this sense, the life of the entire community and the right to continue living is defended, which ultimately, could ensure the stability of the human being from its integrity [16].

Consequently, an alternative form of the relationship between man and the earth is conceived, having an ethical turn and starting from his role as a member of a biotic community and that his well-being depends on the responses to the interactions of the ecosystemic processes; in addition, the ethical turn must be accompanied by a noticeable change in the attitude of the human being that leads him to a process of awareness that is molded over time and is consolidated by his response to the social and environmental modifications of the environment itself [3]. Although it is given that in the ethics of the Earth, there is total inclusion, this initially generated a conceptual divergence as to the magnitude of the term Earth, since it was strictly referenced as property, for that reason, one of the greatest interpretations was that ethics was inscribed with an economic interest with benefits, mediated by conveniences and utilities but not as obligations for the human being due to the exclusion of all other organisms on Earth [16]. Likewise, towards the 80s, another aspect against the constitution of the Earth's ethics was aspects that were related to the fact of giving an intrinsic value to nature, which derived between valuing nature and the good of humanity, and the discussions of the valuations of natural resources [3].

- Global Bioethics, Van Rensselaer Potter in the 70s raised the term as an alternative to the neglected Ethics of the Earth, was based on biological knowledge and human value systems, that is, an integrative vehicle, such is the scope that is composed of two ethics, medical and ecological [2]; in such a way that its purpose

is human health and environmental health, said interaction seeks the well-being of ecosystems, biotic systems and the human species [16]. According to the ethics proposed by Potter in 1971, it is a multidimensional integrative ethic that can address all types of problems, which requires actions based on values and biological facts, to the extent that the value of the system is constituted, the survival of the ecosystem is achieved [17]; as a complement, Potter established from his bioethical creed that it is necessary *to join a global movement that makes possible the survival and a more beneficial development of humanity in harmony with the natural environment.* [3].

Global bioethics, also considered the science of survival, uses knowledge for the existence and improvement of humanity, acting as a bridge between the technical-scientific agency and the reflexive plurality of the human sciences, having as its fundamental support the human population density on Earth. Potter considers responsibility as a key concept, he considers it the necessary vehicle to forge the values and principles about life and the Earth and the care of these, for this, a horizontal point of view is necessary that in the set of relationships includes the ecosystem and humanity [16]. Likewise, global bioethics must explore alternative forms of relationship between human beings and nature with the mediation of ethics and aesthetics, which directly impact subjective aspects of the individual such as depression, apathy, and emotional fatigue, which can be harmful to the survival of the human species and the biotic community of the Earth [18].

- Environmental Ethics, since the 90s, there has been a tendency to give ethics a status of differential route and is presented as an integrative proposal that by deepening the founding approaches of Jahr, Leopold, and Potter strengthens the ethical actions of the human being towards the total protection of all life [19]. The proposal of environmental ethics grants more argumentative force in the context of the exploration and analysis of existing natural phenomena and broadens the knowledge of their dynamics and effects, consequently, it would increase the probability of establishing and implementing responsible actions in the face of the growing deterioration of ecosystems [20].

In the field of environmental ethics, the importance and *notable relevance are highlighted because it denotes the recognition of moral value for non-human beings at the same level as that of humans* [21]; therefore, it would be assumed that there has been a moral differentiation and a distancing of the human being from his environment. Environmental ethics is based on the change of *view on the relationship of man with nature*, given the effect of anthropic actions on his environment *classified as the causal agent of the ecological imbalance on the planet.* [3].

Consequently, it is noted that environmental ethics must have an ethics of culture that is solidified when respect founds all human relationships and with an ethics-aesthetics given the complex systems of interrelations that are formed and structured by physical elements and inclusive elements such as symbols and ways of life, which ultimately are interlocutors that total the ecosystems and finally constitute the Earth [22]. In addition, based on Potter's theoretical postulates, emphasis is placed on interpersonal, socioeconomic, and political relationships of human beings to address environmental dilemmas [23]; however, the approach to the dilemmas involves the interaction of man as an individual and of the collective, together with the environment and the biosphere [16].

- Ecological Bioethics is born from an interrelation between two types of ethics, Leopold's Earth Ethics and Potter's Global Bioethics, in terms of the extension to the inclusion of biotic communities and the control of human density, both of which directly impact the survival of all life forms; for ecological bioethics, the central axis is found in the valorization of the survival of the species supported by the current situation of lack of control of fertility, the accelerated increase in population and the lack of valorization of the ecosystem; in a complementary way, Potter proposes that within the framework of ecological bioethics the problems to be addressed must be long-term ones, where the preservation of ecosystems is raised in a compatible way that leads to the continuity of the human species [16].

Furthermore, to return to Potter's original idea about the need to establish environmental bioethics that allows for the adoption of multidisciplinary to study and understand current environmental problems; this allows us to visualize an alternative route for analyzing human behavior, having as a background the

attachment to its environment with the inclusion of dimensions such as cultural, religious, and economic, among others, and where the generation of environmental behaviors adjusted to its reality and way of thinking is promoted, and not against nature itself and life itself.

- Planetary Ethics proposes that the approach to this ethic is multidimensional and the approach to its analysis must be binding and relational between complex bioethics and ecosophy. [17], using the comprehensive hermeneutic methodology as a disciplinary trans-method, to contribute towards a new way of living on the planet [24]. In addition, it can be expanded by pointing out that complex bioethics and ecosophy aim to permeate the human being from his being, promoting two processes, a de-linking and a re-linking in favor of respect for life that leads to a new spiritual sense of being, from a soul that gives love to the metacognition of transformation.
- Ecoethics emerged in the 2000s with a high affinity with two predecessor ethics, environmental ethics and ecological bioethics. The concept is amplified by pointing out that the *fundamental object is the reflection on complex structures and organizations*, emphasizing that this ethic *constitutes a true revolution* because it must lead to a transformation in the conception of rights for all organisms that inhabit the planet and delves into the rigor of the complex interactions of living beings that are found in a certain habitat [12]. Furthermore, talking about eco ethics is:
An invitation to have broader connotations and with greater existential and emotional meaning, is to place the experience of wonder and marvel before the whole of life, that is, to have as a vision the Earth, nature, and the phenomenon of life [12].

Likewise, there is the evolutionary process of ethics and human actions, ecoethics must be focused on conservation, otherwise, that is, more pragmatic and conscious with an ultimate goal, that of maintaining life, in other words, that translates into an ethics of life, the ethics of being and the ethics of responsibility [10]. As a complement to the above, Ecoethics is the *behavior derived from the full recognition of our dependence on the other, which is our Oikos, everything that makes biological humanity possible* [25].

However, the need to establish a series of ecological tributes for eco-ethics is also visible, which allows studying *the practical implications of human conflicts based on principles, theories, and moral values*. [26]For the latter, the moral argumentation of the relationships between human beings and the natural environment has been lacking, since only the social or cultural perspective has had a strong vision, therefore, they invite us to make up for these deficiencies in ecoethics.

In this same sense, it is indicated that eco ethics arises as a response to the current degradation of the environment where human life occurs, which must be referenced to address it in complexity with the values and principles required by applied ethics, which is born from individual to collective morality, in this particular case, to all disciplinary sectors that impact the environment with their activities [27].

3.2 Ethical pillars for life

- From the Ethics of the Earth proposed by Leopold, an opening is given to a proposal that is defined as *Ecocentrism*, in which it is considered as a pillar for the ethics of life, where *the human species is one more element that exists and interacts in the framework of biotic communities*. , and a [28]system of values anchored in nature is established, where human nature is not the only bearer of intrinsic values [19]. In this pillar, *ethics invites the expansion of the moral frontier aimed at the inclusion of all living beings and all the elements that make up the ecosystems*, without granting moral status to any component of the planet, which translates into moral co-responsibility [3]. The above encourages the defense of total equality between the various biotic beings and the abiotic components of nature, that is, there would be no differentiation between human and non-human beings [29]; consequently, if this type of relationship were established, it becomes an alternative route and a worldview directed towards the ethics of life could be reached.
- From the Global Bioethics proposed by Potter and in consequence with the proposal of the Ethics of the Earth, which proposes an ecological establishment of life, *Biocentrism arises*, considered as a second

pillar, where its philosophical position claims the primordial value of life leading to the premise that all beings deserve moral respect [19]; decentralizing the human being in the conception of nature, towards a broader and more inclusive vision, the human as part of a whole that includes and of which it is part, the bios. [2]. Likewise, biocentrism supports the existence of value in all living beings, for this reason, biodiversity becomes the center of the universe, in addition, there is respect towards sentient and non-sentient beings as a symbiosis where there is equality of considerations to exist and live independently of the species [29]. In this pillar, the vital force flows from the center to the periphery, in this transit, the necessary conditions and possibility of existence are given to everything that make up the ecosystems that fulfill a function directly or indirectly and have a purpose within the entire biotic-abiotic framework for which they have evolved [1].

- On the other hand, within the dynamics of the route towards the defined pillars of ecocentrism and biocentrism, it is important to refer to a relational pillar of those recently mentioned, reference is made to *Expansionism*, considered as a transformative step from the anthropocentric vision towards the expansion of the borders of morality by the human being towards other non-human beings, in the transformation that could be holistic or total for an adequate moral expansion; However, the ethical path in which expansionism was forged was generating individual approaches and approximations, such as zoocentrism, where the balance tipped towards the valuation of the zoological scale, which would ultimately lead to a new imbalance, due to the obligation to grant an intrinsic value to life [21].
- Similarly to the proposed pillars, an additional one is proposed, the *Transforming Agent pillar* for ethics, given all the mechanisms and actions that can be derived and led to the ethics of life, bioethics addresses the urgent need for a reform of thought based on new knowledge in the human being to generate a re-civilization process where there is a clear perception between the occurrence of actions and the awareness of their meaning and effects [17]; In addition, the transformation must include a process to re-civilize thought along with the cognitive aspect of thinking, which must include interdisciplinary knowledge to eliminate the multiple blindnesses of the human being.

As a complement, in the fourth pillar *Transforming Agent* it is important to establish an ethic that in ecological terms commits the human being that not only are the conceptual recognitions must also make an *ethical turn* in their actions, motivated to a profound change in the being directed to reach an ecological conscience that has as a fundamental principle that of coherence in the action, therefore, it is urgent to limit the human being in his works, and thus be able to establish a path of struggle for the existence of humanity; If the conversion to a new form of conscience occurs, under the point of view of ecology, a political character is imprinted on the human being since it must be reflected in the individual and collective responsibility of their actions *to preserve the health of the Earth*. [16], specifically, *the permanence of authentic human life on Earth* [30], *that life is respected and the environment is cared for, since well-preserved resources create a bridge to a better future* [31], that awareness is raised about each of the actions, turning human beings into citizens with a culture of responsibility [32].

In addition, and in terms of relational and functional terms to involve the four pillars mentioned, the *Ecology of the individual* must be a founding component in the ethical turn of the relationship between human beings and nature; it starts from the typology of the human being as an agent of destruction and threat to the existence of biotic communities to the typology of the human being characterized by love, respect, admiration, and appreciation for life. In this transition, Leopold forges an ecological obligation with all the components of the biotic community and the earth [16], likewise, there is the ecological perspective focused on a limitation of the freedom of action of the struggle of the human species and the way of guiding the assessment of environmental situations that individually would generate divergences in the social field and that could not be discerned by a single individual [3].

Continuing with the above, a relational context can be defined between ethics and politics, referring to how the spiritual connection of man is when he relates to nature, which should not be only as a guarantee for its exploitation, on the contrary, the relationships can occur in various orders with the intervention of dynamic exploratory processes from sensations to symbolic resignifications in which the footprint of the human being is respectful of nature [33].

In the context of limits, from an ecological perspective, it is necessary to involve the interrelation of individual and collective subjectivity with the social practices that are leading to the progressive deterioration of the biotic community and the Earth, due to which, the ethical turn focuses on subjectivity and the radical biotic and social otherness that will tend towards the reconstruction and creation of collective social values, new affections and new perceptions that allow another form of ethical, aesthetic and political relationship between human beings and nature [16]. Thus, it is made clear that, in the relational context of the individual in his daily life and the hectic social sphere that surrounds him, within the construction of the social project, everything starts with the being and his relational intimacy with the world, where he takes positions of adherence or distancing that allow him to grow in his ethics and build social ethics [34].

- Finally, a fifth pillar is proposed that contributes to the ethics of life, an articulating pillar based on aspects derived from what Guattari proposed with *Ecosophy* as the vehicle that articulates ethics, aesthetics, and politics, through environmental ecology, social ecology, and mental ecology; the interrelation of ecologies in the individual and the collective, will allow the generation of transversal positions with the capacity to analyze the complex existing relationships of the human being with nature and can allow the generation of the necessary changes and reinventions from the level of the being, its immediate family and social environment, to the biological community in general, with medium and long term effects for the achievement of the survival of all forms of life [35].

In addition to the above, they define Ecosophy as a constitutive category that allows to uniting of broad and diverse fields of knowledge generated in philosophy, art, and science, among others; which through inquiry promotes a new understanding of the common home and the ways of inhabiting it, that is, a new relationship of *oikos – ethos*. [36]. In addition to the above, if bioethics is permeated by ecosophy, it leads to a complexification in the continuous search for knowledge in favor of life that contributes to human survival and therefore to the conditions of human life, in this sense, it is transformed and converted towards a new conception of the spirit, giving conception to a spiritual ecology where the deepening of the essence of the human being is achieved [17].

3.3 Aspects for the survival of life

- There is a need for the configuration of concepts and theoretical positions concerning the generation of relational categories to ethics such as ecological bioethics, global bioethics, Earth ethics, ecological ethics, and environmental ethics; these being used to refer to the urgency of the conservation of the Earth together with all its components including all the biotic and non-biotic; also, with a connotation about the fact that, within the biotic, one of the members is the human being that integrates a biological community; in such a way that the fulfillment of the previous connotation is important to avoid contradictions of the actions and to be able to establish an ethical relationship in ecological terms, where an individual and collective responsibility of the human being to take care of life is reflected and therefore, the well-being and health of the Earth [16].
- It is important that the survival of life is addressed from the complexity with an interdisciplinary approach that allows contributing to the change of the being with the construction of thought with greater awareness about the environment, where amid the plurality of language the capacity of discernment in the daily action must be developed, thus, one could appeal to the reason of the human being about the meaning of his being and the plurality of thoughts and knowledge, in translation, the underlying issue is otherness, where the actions of the other question the very way of being. Therefore, the existence of conflicts of ethics marks a position in front of a pluralistic human society, where the moral reason of man arises that confronts the understanding of the new human being [37].
- A strong call is proposed to question how the human-nature relationship has been structured in Western modernity, to call on human beings to rethink from dialectical rationality to *reintegration and ethical commitment to all forms of life*. [38], which is why the invitation to initiate and forge a process of building a conceptual framework that allows for the involvement of all the understandings that occur in the relationship and to understand the orientations towards the protection of life, without differentiation or

distinction of species, that allows for the renewal of the foundation of the survival of life and, therefore, ethics of life, becomes interesting.

- Postulates that are oriented towards the defense and protection of life for all forms of expression of biodiversity must be consolidated. This must involve aspects of a relationship of dependence of people in harmony with nearby or surrounding ecosystems; in this sense, there is a need for environmental regulations adjusted to realities between the areas occupied by people, such as urban and natural areas, promotion of human production and consumption that do not affect natural environments, and the promotion of a guiding role of the ethics of life towards a new structure of relational and functional association between human beings and ecosystems, where the fundamental pillar is the vital interpretation of ecosystems and:

The incorporation of spiritual values that give human beings the conviction that they share with nature by reaching agreements, in this way, the sense of brotherhood of the human species with non-human species that occupy the same space will be reflected [19].

Consequently, actions aimed at protecting and caring for nature become a strategy and an alternative that aims to achieve *the survival of humanity and all non-human beings*. [3].

- The postulates require various supports that allow the inclusion of worldviews and epistemologies to reach a multisystemic reflection that gives way to generating new values for all forms of life existing in the biosphere, consequently, proposing a transdisciplinary reconversion to constitute the art of inhabiting the planet [5]. Likewise, the importance of the translation of key meanings for a holistic and interdisciplinary understanding is pointed out, terms such as *earth, soil, ecosystem, and environment are integrated into the concept of -biosphere- which allows inviting a greater degree of understanding to the ethics of life [39].*

- The generation of a conceptual framework for the ethics of life as a moral strategy to mitigate the environmental crisis is substantial; the following are highlighted as relevant: 1) the human being must *learn to share ecosystems in interaction and reciprocity with all other biotic and abiotic beings [40]2) Respect for life and its environment must be fostered as a critical instance of sustainable development in full coherence with the environment [41]3) The criteria that underpin the ethics of life are justice, human rights, solidarity, and reciprocity, oriented towards the protection of human beings and non-human nature, living or inert. [42]4) the generation of a -bridge or union- between science and ethics proposed by Jahr and Potter that, today, would be a bridge between all of humanity and its common and original place: the biosphere [6], and 5):*

The rescue of the intrinsic values of biodiversity in the context of cultural pluralism and without leaving aside the existence of a factor that supports life identified as an ecosystem, territory, soil, or natural space [3].

- It is essential to rescue in the human being the sense of -being and being- about other beings and places, as an inclusive principle that cares for life, given the current environmental chaos, that is, the bad relationship of the human being with the biosphere, has mainly caused economic disorder, poor technological management and the taking of inadequate decisions of management of natural resources [12]. The above, calls to resume the emerging role of the ethics of life, as a founding principle of a new vision of the relationships of the human being with himself, with the species, and with the *minerals of the planet, and the interconnection of these with the universe; in complement, the ethics of life, refers to the interconnections of the ethical world concerning the interactions of the human being with nature, for which a strong vision of individual and collective responsibility is printed in front of the human being and the same universe. [12].*

- A vital aspect is the ethical conduct with which human beings relate, where it refers to the loss of ethical principles of certain population groups since childhood, which leads as a consequence to the reduction of people's perceptions of ancestral knowledge and to a moral depreciation with nature; sensitizing categories such as [8]relationality, complementarity, and reciprocity stand out, and as emerging categories a, respect for the environment, standards of life and delimitation of functions. Adding to

ethical conduct, it is emphasized that traveling the path of life to maturity seeks happiness and the mark on humanity and that everything *is conditioned to the way each person lives in their being*, in other words, their moral permanence and lifestyle, which should lead them to the ethical task of saving their home and therefore their life that is built from the discernments in their interiority (of everything of their being) and the exteriorities, that is, all the (transitory and accelerated) environment [43].

Likewise, human coexistence is a behavioral process where every individual of every species must be included in the construction of the life project, in which only the guiding principle of respect for life and different others exists [44]; in this way, the basis for the transformation to another possible world made up of symmetrical relationships are established; for the life project to be possible, it must be cemented with the ethics of coexistence to build this new world. Given the connotation of human behaviors towards a life project, the aspect of belonging to humanity and nature is included, it points out that the modern ontology of the human being has established a separation from himself and from everyone, where he has preferred the freedom of his behaviors and actions without responsibility to fulfill the obligations of and for life [45].

Therefore, acting irresponsibly or without taking responsibility for one's actions is the result of the current reality, which is very complex and which influences indirectly and directly the relationship with others. Therefore, an ethical responsibility identified with the care of life is postulated. Responsibility must be practical for human action for the benefit and care of other species, oriented towards an ethic of the future responsible for the ecosystem and its biodiversity, and ultimately, an ethic of life for survival.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis presented in this reflective work starts by showing the postulates that the different ethics have presented since their constitution by founding researchers, their followers, and their detractors, thus allowing an overview of the conceptual and textual evolution that has been forged for approximately a century, that is to say since the 1920s of the twentieth century, about the concepts and positions that the authors allowed themselves to address from the approach that allows conceiving the ethics of life for the survival of all living beings and non-living elements that make up the Earth.

As common elements among the ethics proposed in this work, thus, Bioethics, Earth Ethics, Global Bioethics, Environmental Ethics, Ecological Bioethics, Planetary Ethics and Ecoethics, it is found that a transformation of the visions, attitudes, and behaviors that human beings have with all other existing living organisms and inert elements found on the planet is required; said reconversion should be guided by a conceptual structural framework directed towards acting responsibly, that is, an ethic of life that seeks well-being, balance, permanence, preservation, conservation, and respect for all interacting and existing components on Earth.

Ethical pillars are proposed to make a first approach to the ethics of life that allows the survival of all living and non-living organisms on the planet. Thus, the opening to a horizontality is given by the pillars of ecocentrism, expansionism, and biocentrism, as relational elements in the formation of a new ethical conduct of the human being with its entire environment, where it requires having a leading role and that is why the authors consider it as the transforming Agent that requires a change of all ethical and ecological perspective; Finally, Ecosophy and its principles are proposed as the articulating vehicle for all the pillars.

Finally, aspects necessary to study and debate in the exercise of the formation and constitution of ethics of life for survival are projected, such as the configuration of concepts and theoretical positions, the approach from the complexity with an interdisciplinary focus, the generation of questions that define relational-functional structures of humans with nature, the consolidation of postulates oriented to the defense of life, the generation of a conceptual framework for the ethics of life that rescues in humans the sense of being and being about other living beings and elements, ultimately, the ethical conduct of human relationships.

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